

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS ON LECTURERS COMPUTER LITERACY SKILLS USED IN TEACHING AND LEARNING IN SOUTH EAST COLLEGES OF EDUCATION NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10817652>

Published Date: 14-March-2024

Abstract: This study was carried out to ascertain the Perception of students on lecturers computer literacy skills Acquired and Used in teaching and learning in South East Colleges of Education, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study while one null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Design of the study was a descriptive survey. The population comprised 2,102 lecturers and 10,500 students in all the seven colleges of Education in south east Nigeria. The sample size was 630 and 450 drawn from the population using accidental sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire titled Computer Literacy Skills Use Questionnaire (CLSUQ) which contain 20 items questions on computer literacy skills and was validated by two experts all from Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University The reliability of the instruments was established Cronbach alpha technique for CLSUQ to test for internal consistency of the items which yielded reliability index of 0.82 respectively. A total of 671 and 510 copies of instrument were distributed to respondents but 630 and 450 copies were collected and properly filled given 94% return rate. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and independent sample t-test. The findings of the study reveal among others that, lecturers often use Microsoft word in teaching and learning. Furthermore, Internet operation, microsoft powerpoint and microsoft excel were rarely used by Colleges of Education lecturers for teaching and learning. More so, there is a significant difference in the mean score of lecturers usage of computer literacy skills in teaching and learning differs significantly. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that colleges of education lecturers should constantly update their knowledge in computer skills for teaching and research through constant practices, conferences, seminars and workshops.

Keywords: Lecturers, Computer Literacy skills, Usage, Teaching and Learning, Colleges of Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer is a sharp method adopted to help the common sense of man, a catalyst to innovation development, effective and efficient management in all spheres of human endeavours are competently handled by computers (Mbam, 2012). Computers are being used in wide range of operations like multi media for video and music, producing typed document, saving for future use, presentation of data, telephone lines, for communications and scanner for hard document duplication.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 11, Issue 1, pp: (73-78), Month: January - February 2024, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

One can only use computer and computer gadgets when he or she is computer literate. Literacy is the ability to read and write one's own name and further for knowledge and interest, write coherently, and think critically about the written word. According to Katane and Selvi (2009), literacy is a set of knowledge, and experience necessary for future which manifests in activities. Literacy, according to Harvey (2008) is the quality of being well qualified physical and intellectually. Furthermore, Harvey defined literacy as the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities at a level of expertise sufficient for one to be able to perform in an appropriate work setting (within or outside academia).

The literacy aspect of a computer system dwells much on the practical knowledge of computer. usage is the act of employing or putting into service. According to Ndawi, Thomas and Nyaruwata (2013), researchers over the years had generally supported that computer skills utilization in education have many benefits for teachers. These include, sending and receiving of mails, setting of examination questions, increasing teacher's efficiency in preparation and content delivery. Lecturers in colleges of education are expected to use their knowledge of computing skills in teaching and learning.

The key fundamental areas of computer literacy skills needed by Colleges of education lecturers for effective performance are the computer literacy skills such as Microsoft word operation, Internet Operation, Microsoft powerpoint and Microsoft excel. These key areas were investigated by the researcher to establish the college of education lecturers level of utilization of such skills. College of Education is the unit of tertiary education in Nigeria saddled with the responsibility of training teachers to obtain non-degree but qualitative professional certificate in education. According to Jegede and Owolabi (2014), use of computer by lecturers is improperly handled in south east Colleges of Education. However, computer use in the classroom settings is being handled by lecturers, they are the personnel to impact the knowledge to students. From other works reviewed it shows that lecturers don't make use of the aforementioned computer literacy skills, they do not consider use of computers as part of their normal activities.

Problem statement

Most of the lecturers in Colleges of Education in south-east Nigeria, have phobia in operation of computer system; they prefer to use the old method of teaching which is teacher -centred (traditional) method of teaching. They also find it difficult to cope with the technology age probably because they have acclimatized with the copying of notes on the board or dictating the notes for the students. Being a computer literate is the basic necessity for lecturers to properly deliver lectures in different field of specialization, therefore computer literacy skill is a must for all lecturers in Colleges of Education. Despite various initiatives and programmes by the government to incorporate computer literacy skill in education, not much research had been done to evaluate evaluate if computer literacy skills acquired and used by lecturers is influenced by school type, and gender. This study filled the gap of lack of current information pertaining to the computer literacy skills use by lecturers in Colleges of Education in teaching in South east Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate perception of students' on acquisition of computer literacy skills for teaching and learning by Colleges of Education lecturers in south east Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to investigate;

1. lecturers on the usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power point and Excel) for teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in south east Nigeria?
2. perception of students on lecturers usage of computer literacy skills Microsoft word, Internet operation, Microsoft powerpoint and Microsoft Excel in teaching and learning?

Research Question

1. What are the mean scores of lecturers on the usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power point and Excel) for teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in south east Nigeria?
2. What are the mean rating scores of students on their lecturers usage of computer literacy skills Microsoft word, Internet operation, Microsoft powerpoint and Microsoft Excel in teaching and learning?

Hypothesis

H0 Mean rating scores of lecturers' and students on the lecturers usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Microsoft Power point and Excel) in teaching do not differ significantly.

2. METHODOLOGY

The design adopted for this research was descriptive survey method which aims at assessing the perception of students on lecturers computer literacy skills used in teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in South-east Nigeria. According to Nworgu (2015) a descriptive survey research are those studies which aim at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics features or facts about a given population. The study was conducted using questionnaire designed to be descriptive. The total population of the study comprises of ten thousand five hundred (10, 500) students and Two thousand one hundred and two (2,102) lecturers in the seven Colleges of Education in South east Nigeria. Accidental sampling technique was employed in selecting students and lecturers from the seven Colleges of Education in the south East, which yield a total sample size of 630 for lecturers and 450 for students. Computer literacy skills Used Questionnaire was designed (CLSUQ) which contain 20 items on computer literacy skills used by lecturers and students. Copies of the questionnaire were given to the lecturers and students in their various schools. They were asked to complete the questionnaire using a five point scale from; Always, Often, Occasionally, Rarely and Never. The data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. To test the null hypotheses independent t-test was used, the hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

3. RESULTS

Research question 1

What are the mean scores of lecturers on the usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power point and Excel) in teaching in colleges of education in south east Nigeria.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation sores in computer literacy skills used by colleges of education lecturers.

N = 630

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	REMARK
MICROSOFT WORD				
1	I use word processing to prepare students assessment record	4.14	0.74	Often
2	I use Microsoft word to give students assignment	3.88	0.82	Often
3	I assess students document on CD or flash drive using word processing	4.05	0.78	Often
4	I use word processing to type my students examination question	4.01	0.78	Often
5	I use word to prepare my note of lessons	4.11	0.75	Often
	Sub total =	4.04	0.77	Often
INTERNET OPERTAION				
6	I use Internet to send information via e-mails to the students	3.94	0.81	Often
7	I give students assignment to search on internet.	4.09	0.79	Often
8	I use Google class room with my students	4.13	0.80	Often
9	I use zoom to interact with my students	2.98	1.24	Rarely
10	I use internet to upload students results	2.15	1.10	Rarely
	Subtotal =	2.74	0.95	Rarely
MICROSOFT POWER POINT				
11	I use power point to present Animation in teaching	2.14	1.11	Rarely
12	I use power point to print out slides on note of lessons	2.30	1.06	Rarely
13	I use power point slide to present a note of lesson to the students	2.19	1.08	Rarely
14	I use Microsoft word .in place of microsoft powerpoint to display a slide	2.21	1.09	Rarely
15	I use more than two slides in teaching	2.27	1.06	Rarely
	Subtotal =	2.22	1.08	Rarely
ITEMS				
	MICROSOFT EXCEL	\bar{X}	SD	
16	I use Excel in computing students grade	2.21	1.11	Rarely
17	I use excel to sort figures in ascending order	2.17	1.06	Rarely
18	I use excel to create graph	2.10	1.08	Rarely
19	I calculate numerical data using excel	2.09	1.01	Rarely
20	I use excel to prepare lecture note	2.21	1.11	Rarely
	Subtotal =	2.1	1.07	Rarely
	Grand Total	2.79	0.97	

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Table 2: The summary of the computer literacy skills utilized by Colleges of Education lecturers for teaching and Research is presented in Table 4.

S/N	COMPUTER LITERACY SKILLS	\bar{X}	SD	REMARK
1	Microsoft word	4.04	0.77	Often
2	Internet operation	2.74	0.95	Rarely
3	Microsoft power point	2.22	1.08	Rarely
4	Microsoft excel	2.15	1.07	Rarely
TOTAL		2.78	0.96	

The findings in table 4 reveals the results of computer literacy skills utilized by lecturers in colleges of Education as contain in item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, hence they do not utilize item 9,10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20. The data in table 5 show mean and standard deviation of lecturers computer literacy skills as contained in table 5, from indication lecturers often use microsoft word in teaching with mean score of 4.04. Furthermore, Internet operation, Microsoft power point and microsoft excel skills were rarely used by lecturers as contained in table 5 above.

Research question 2:

What are the mean perception Score of Students used on the Computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet Operation, Power point and Microsoft Excel.) used by their lecturers in teaching.

TABLE 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of students response on lecturers usage of computer literacy skills in teaching.

N= 450

S/N0	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	REMARK
MICFOSOFT WORD				
1	My lecturers uses word processing to prepare students assessment record	4.20	0.78	Often
2	My lecturers uses Microsoft word to give students assignment	4.33	0.74	Often
3	My lecturers assesses students document on CD or flash drive using word processing	4.41	0.68	Often
4	My lecturers uses word processing to type my students examination question	4.25	0.79	Often
5	My lecturers uses Microsoft word to prepare my note of lessons	4.22	0.78	Often
Subtotal =		4.2	0.75	Often
INTERNET OPERTAION				
6	My lecturer uses Internet to send information via e-mails to the students	4.02	0.88	Often
7	My lecturer give students assignment to search on internet.	4.05	0.88	Often
8	My lecturer uses Google class room with my students	4.21	0.83	Often
9	My lecturer uses zoom to interact with my students	4.03	0.93	Often
10	My lecturer uses internet to upload students results	4.00	0.91	Often
Subtotal =		4.06	0.88	
ITEMS MICROSOFT POWER POINT				
		\bar{X}	SD	
11	My lecturer uses power point to present Animation in teaching	3.54	1.29	Often
12	My lecturer uses power point to print out note of lessons in slides	2.63	1.04	Rarely
13	My lecturer uses power point to present a note of lesson to the students	2.46	1.02	Rarely
14	My lecturer can display slides without microsoft powerpoint softwares.	3.41	1.27	Occasionally
15	My lecturer can create more than two slides in microsoft powerpoint.	2.25	1.08	Rarely
Subtotal =		2.86	1.14	
MICROSOFT EXCEL				
16	My lecturer uses Excel in computing students grade	2.45	1.01	Rarely
17	My lecturer uses excel to teach students how to sort figures in ascending order	2.84	1.05	Occasionally
18	My lecturer uses excel to create graph	2.72	1.02	Occasionally
19	My lecturer calculates numerical data using excel	3.10	1.16	Occasionally
20	My lecturer gives assignment on excel	2.71	1.05	Occasionally
Sub total =		2.66	1.06	Rarely
Grand Total		2.97	0.96	

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Table 1 and 2: The summary of the computer literacy skills utilized by Colleges of Education lecturers for teaching and Research is presented in Table 7.

	COMPUTER LITERACY SKILLS	LECTURERS		REMARK	STUDENTS		REMARK
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
1	Microsoft word	4.2	0.77	Often	2.28	0.75	Rarely
2	Internet operation	2.74	0.95	Occasionally	4.06	0.89	Often
3	Microsoft power point	2.22	1.08	Rarely	2.85	1.14	Occasionally
4	Microsoft excel	2.16	1.07	Rarely	2.66	1.06	Occasionally
	TOTAL	2.83	0.96		2.96	0.96	

Table 1 and 2 shows the mean and standard deviation scores of lecturers and students, on the lecturers usage of computer literacy skills in teaching and learning. The results from Table 2 shows that lecturers utilize computer literacy skills in item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 14, and 19 also lecturers do not utilize computer literacy skills as contain in item 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, and 20 considering students as response. The findings in table 1 reveal the results of computer literacy skills utilized by lecturers in colleges of Education as contain in item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, hence they do not utilize item 9,10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20. Lecturers do not utilize computer literacy skills considering the mean scores and standard deviation on individual items in Table 2, mean score of 2.83 and Standard deviation score of 0.96 for lecturers and mean score of 2.96 and standard deviation score of 0.96 for students.

Null hypothesis

The mean scores of lecturers and students of college of education on the lecturers’ usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power-point and Excel) in teaching and learning will not differ significantly.

Table 1 t-test on the mean scores of lecturers and students on the lecturers’ usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power-point and Excel) in teaching and learning

Computer literacy skills	Source of variation	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	Cal.t	P. value	$P \geq 0.05$
MSword	Lecturers	630	20.20	2.56	978	7.60	0.000	Sig
	Students	350	21.43	2.10				
Internet Operation	Lecturers	630	17.30	2.73	978	16.64	0.000	Sig
	Students	350	20.31	2.69				
Power Point	Lecturers	630	11.13	4.37	978	20.39	0.000	Sig
	Students	350	17.34	4.91				
Excel	Lecturers	630	10.79	4.27	978	17.42	0.000	Sig
	Students	350	15.88	4.57				

In table 1, it was observed that at 0.05 level of significance and 978df the calculated t is 7.60 on MS Word with the calculated P.value 0.000 and t16.64 for internet with Pvalue 0.000, t20.39 for Power-point with cal. P.value 0.000 and t17.42 for MS.Excel with cal. P.value 0.000 which are less than 0.05, the mean scores of lecturers and students in college of education on the lecturers usage on computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet operation, Power-point and MS Excel) in teaching, differ significantly. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

4. DISCUSSION

Lecturers computer literacy skills used in teaching and learning in South east colleges of Education

The outcome of the analysis in Table 1 for answering research question 4, indicates that lecturers utilize Microsoft word skills, all the Microsoft word items were often used by lecturers. In internet operation skills, lecturers rarely utilize item 9 and 10. Generally from indication as shown in table 1, out of 5 items in internet operation skills they utilize 3. Therefore, lecturers demonstrate low in utilization of internet operation, Microsoft power point and Microsoft excel. Their low performance in the utilization of internet, Microsoft power point and excel could be that there was no steady light, internet facilities and stand by projector in their various schools to aid teaching. This result is in agreement with Louis et al (2010) who reported that most of Africans are yet to embrace computer utilization appropriately. Unfortunately, in Nigeria

colleges of education, lecturers are still struggling with outdated gadgets in place of new technologies. (Ansarki, Ayub & Kadir, 2015).

Students Perception on lecturers usage of computer literacy skills

The findings of this present study from table 2 shows that lecturers in colleges of education do not utilize computer literacy skills. The mean score of lecturers and students on lecturers usage of computer literacy skills (Microsoft word, Internet Operation , power point and excel) in teaching differ significantly, lecturers had a least mean score of 2.97 while students had the higher mean score of 3.49. According to the finding on Table 2, the students mean score on lecturers usage of computer literacy skills differs significantly, this is because the p-value (0.000) is less than critical value (0.05). This findings is in agreement with Isiyaku (2013), included the desire of the Nigerian Government to ensure uniformity of content and educational standard. From the result of this finding as shown in table 2 on students response, it shows that students graded their lecturers higher in computer literacy skills, which could be that some lecturers have source of help in using computer, either from friends or family member, that is why students could not recognize their level of computer literacy in teaching, as shown in table 1 and 2 of the research question.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that computer literacy skills are fairly utilized by colleges of education lecturers considering students response. The most used skills by lecturers were Microsoft word and internet operation in teaching and learning. Microsoft power point and excel were utilized by lecturers in teaching and learning. However, students response influenced lecturers in Colleges of Education usage of computer literacy skills in teaching and learning in south east, Nigeria.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Colleges of education lecturers should enhance their skills regularly and stay up to date in technology such as computing skills through continual professional development trainings and workshops. They should be sent for in-service training, seminars and workshop on how to fully incorporate computer literacy skills in any mode of instruction in teaching and learning processes.
2. Government should provide internet facilities and adequate computer facilities in the colleges of education for constant usage among lecturers, especially lecturers in south east, Nigeria in order to facilitate their lecturing activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Harvey, L. (2008). Analytic quality glossary. Quality Research International. Retrieved October, 14, 2011, from <http://www.qualityresearchinternational.com/glossary/>
- [2] Jegede, S. and Owolabi, F. (2014). *The Third Millenium Secretary and Information and Communication Teaching*. Published by Nemax Ltd. Enugu.
- [3] Katane. T. and Selvi, H. (2009). Teachers competence and further education as priorities for sustainable development of rural schools in Latvia. *Journal of Teacher Education and Training*. 6,41 -.51
- [4] Mbam, B.C (2012). *Computer literacy and operation*. Green Light Computers. N0 28 New Market Road Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Pages 2-3.
- [5] Mbam, B.C (2012). *Computer literacy and operation*. Green Light Computers. N0 28 New Market Road Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Pages 2-3.
- [6] Ndawi, V.E., Thomas, K.A., & Nyanwata, T.L. (2013). Barriers to effective integrations of Information and communication technology in Harere secondary school, *International Journal of Science and Research. (IJSR)*, 2(9), 211-216.
- [7] Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Educational research basic issues and methodology*. (3rded.) Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.